

Time-Independent Schrodinger Equation as Balanced Pressure - Velocity Flow Equation?

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In a previous note (1), it was shown that for a ground state oscillator wavefunction, one could analyse the problem in momentum space as a free gas of momentum particles and obtain $\exp(-p^2/2mT)$ as $f_p \cdot f_p$, f_p being the momentum wavefunction. A free energy equal to zero was obtained, with kinetic energy being the energy term in E-TS. This suggests quantum particles scatter (with conservation of momentum) like classical point particles in momentum space, but differ from classical point particles in position space. In particular, one takes a Fourier transform of f_p as it seems that each momentum wave carries an $\exp(ipx)$ function which is a sort of “baggage” term, possibly due to zitterbewegung. This seems to explain why a free gas in momentum space for the ground state oscillator yields a Gaussian density with $W(x)=\exp(-ax^2)$ ($W(x)$ =wavefunction). An oscillator potential is then needed to keep this density with its momentum space pressure in balance. Thus, quantum mechanics and classical statistical mechanics become very similar for this scenario. This begs the question: What about other potentials or oscillator states higher than the ground state? In such a case, it still seems that one may consider “particles colliding in momentum space” with each carrying an $\exp(ipx)$ “baggage” term, but one does not have a “classical statistical mechanical” equilibrium scenario any longer. Rather, it seems that one has a net force created by $-dV/dx$ ($V(x)$ =potential) and a difference in pressure d/dx [Average(p^2) $d(x)$] where $d(x)$ is density. There also seems to be an average velocity $(1/W)dW/dx$. In momentum space such a velocity would not exist for $f(p)=f(-p)$, but because of the baggage of $\exp(ipx)$ it is present i.e. $p \exp(ipx) - p \exp(-ipx)$. Newton’s law, with force acting on this velocity appears in the equation d/dx [Average(p^2) $d(x)$]= $F(x) d(x)$. This same equation is equivalent to the gradient of the time-independent Schrodinger equation.

For quantum mechanics, one has one particle rather than many as in classical statistical mechanics. Thus, it seems that this “Newton’s law” balance is based on a long term time average. It seems, however, that there should be a period T during which the average can establish itself. After this, one would have periodic time motion where the system keeps scattering back into itself in this characteristic time. This period can be deduced, it seems, from the time-independent Schrodinger equation and is found to be E , the energy.

Ground State Oscillator

It is known that the ground state quantum oscillator has $f_p=\exp(-p^2/2mT)$ which matches the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution for velocity. Thus, it appears that in momentum space one has point particles scattering elastically with conservation of momentum and maximization of entropy. This begs the question: Why then isn’t the density constant as in a classical statistical gas? The reason seems to be that each momentum particle is represented by $\exp(ipx)$ so there is a kind of “spatial baggage”. This spatial baggage creates a spatial density so the momentum

pressure is now confined to this spatial density leading to a pressure distribution which needs to be balanced by a force. In the case of the ground state oscillator, a classical looking balance can occur i.e. $\text{constant} \frac{d}{dx} d(x) = F(x) d(x)$ where $d(x) = W(x)W(x)$. Then $d(x) = \exp(-V(x)/P(\text{constant}))$ Where $V(x)$ is the potential, $F(x) = -d/dx V(x)$ and $P(\text{constant})$ is the constant momentum space pressure. In general, such a balance dependent only on the spatial gradient of density is not created in quantum mechanics, rather there is an accelerated velocity.

Average Velocity in Quantum Mechanics

If one has classical point particles and $f(p) = f(-p)$ (as in $\exp(-p^2/2mT)$), then for every $p, -p$ pair, the average is zero. Such is not the case in quantum mechanics as one has:

$$p \exp(ipx) - p \exp(-ipx) = 2i p \sin(px)$$

Thus, for a wavefunction $W(x) = \sum p f_p \cos(px)$, $u = (1/W) d/dx W$ seems to represent an average velocity. If a force is present due to $V(x)$, then there should be acceleration. In such a case, one might immediately apply Newton's law to obtain a term $2u du/dx$. There is, however, a pressure created by the momentum particles which are forced into a density pattern by the $\exp(ipx)$ baggage. This pressure counterbalances some of the force from $V(x)$ it seems. Alternatively, one may consider a spatial pressure term (with the $\exp(ipx)$ baggage) and equate it to a force, just as is done in classical statistical mechanics (2), but with the pressure being of a different form due to the $\exp(ipx)$ baggage.

$$\frac{d}{dx} [\text{Average}(p^2) d(x)] = F(x) d(x) \quad ((1))$$

Here $F(x) = -d/dx V(x)$, $d(x) = W(x)W(x)$. One applies the gradient d/dx to the pressure $= [\text{Average}(p^2) d(x)]$ because one wants the pressure difference between two points. Furthermore, one should see a $m u d/dx u$ emerging from this equation where $u = (1/W) d/dx W$ as there is a u velocity which should be accelerated. To see the form of $u du/dx$ consider:

Consider $u = p \exp(ipx)$ acted on by a force. Then:

$$u du/dx \text{ is proportional to } i p^3$$

This seems to imply a form for $u du/dx$, namely:

$$u du/dx \text{ is proportional to } (-1/m) (d/dx)^3 W(x) / W(x) \quad ((2))$$

Let us now calculate: $d/dx [\text{Average}(p^2) d(x)] \quad ((2.5))$

$$\text{Average}(p^2) = (-1/2m) (1/W) d/dx d/dx W \quad ((3))$$

To see this in more detail consider a single $\exp(ipx)$. Then ((3)) becomes:

$$(-1/2m) (-p^2).$$

If there is a wavefunction $W(x) = \sum_p f_p \cos(px)$, then ((3)) is similar, except that $1/W(x)$ is now the normalization constant i.e. $\sum_p f_p \cos(px)/W(x)$ is a kind of probability (which sums to 1 in a sum over p).

Thus ((2.5)) becomes:

$$d/dx [W d/dx d/dx W] = (d/dx W) (d/dx d/dx W) + (d/dx)^3 W \quad ((4))$$

The second term on the RHS of ((4)) is proportional to $u d/dx u$. Thus, it seems one may use the idea of a pressure in momentum space, modified by the "spatial baggage" $\exp(ipx)$ to balance the force. Unlike classical statistical mechanics, this will give rise to an average velocity $u = (1/W) d/dx W$ which should be accelerated according to Newton's law. It is, but there is also the extra first term on the RHS of ((4)).

Equation ((1)) then becomes the gradient of the time-independent Schrodinger equation. If one is able to remove the gradient from both sides, one obtains the time dependent Schrodinger equation:

$$(-1/2m) (1/W) d/dx d/dx W + V(x) = E \quad ((5))$$

Thus, the force - pressure balance leads to a kind of conservation of energy equation ((5)) which is the time-independent Schrodinger equation. At first one might feel that E is simply a constant and that there is no real new physics in ((5)) compared to ((1)), but it seems ((5)) is important due to the fact that the "pressure" calculated in ((1)) is due to an average.

Pressure as an Average

In this note, we have talked of pressure and u a kind of average velocity, but these are based on an average of momenta taken over time. In a quantum bound system, one has a single particle that can only be in one p state at a time. Thus, it takes some time for $W(x) = \sum_p f_p \cos(px)$ to be "created", i.e. the system has to cycle through the p 's for some time until one sees a reasonable $W(x)$. This cycling will continue, thus it seems that the system is periodic in time. The question then becomes: What is the period? If one multiplies ((5)) by $W(x)$ and writes $V(x)$ and $W(x)$ as Fourier series, then one obtains:

$$(-1/2m) p^2 f_p \exp(ipx) + \sum_{k+j=p} V_k f_j \exp(ipx) = E f_p \exp(ipx) \quad ((6))$$

$\exp(ipx)$ can be canceled from ((6)). Thus, for every p , one has an equation with the same E on the RHS. The right hand side seems to have the form of $i\frac{d}{dt} W(t)$ implying $W(t)=\exp(iEt)$. This suggests that E is the period of cycling needed to create the average described in the sections above.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue quantum mechanics and classical mechanics are similar in momentum space, with collisions occurring between various momenta p , becoming almost identical for the ground state oscillator. The difference seems to be that in quantum mechanics, the momenta carry a spatial “baggage” term $\exp(ipx)$ which is involved in creating a pressure density which would not normally occur in classical statistical mechanics. Thus, for a classical statistical gas in a box, $F(p)=C\exp(-p^2/2mT)$, the density is constant in space. For the quantum case, there is a spatial density obtained by taking a Fourier transform of $\exp(-bp^2)$ to get a wavefunction of the form $\exp(-a p^2)$ and then the density from $W(x)W(x)$. This spatial density containing momentum pressure requires an oscillator potential to balance it. We suggest that a balance of pressure, given by $\frac{d}{dx} \text{Average}(p^2)d(x)$, where $d(x)=\text{density}$ with force, given by $-dV/dx$, yields the gradient of the Schrodinger equation. This gradient equation contains a term proportional to $(\frac{d}{dx})^3 W$, which is related to $m u \frac{d}{dx} u$ (from the gradient of Newton’s conservation of energy) where $u=(1/W) \frac{d}{dx} W$ which is an average flux created because p and $-p$ don’t cancel for $f(p)=f(-p)$ due to the spatial “baggage” terms (due possibly to zitterbewegung) $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$. The gradient of the Schrodinger equation, leads to the Schrodinger equation which can be interpreted as having an $\exp(iEt)$ term representing cycling through various momenta which make up $W(x)=\text{Sum over } p \text{ } f(p) \cos(px)$.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. The Time Independent Schrodinger Equation as Free Energy Equal to Zero for the Ground State Oscillator (preprint, zenodo, 2019)
2. Reif, F. Fundamentals of Thermal and Statistical Mechanics (Wiley, NY: 1987)